

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D7.8: 3rd Report on Dissemination Activities

WP7 – Dissemination

This project has received funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation
programme under grant agreement No 649493

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	649493	Acronym	STEP	
Full Project Title	Societal and political engagement of young people in environmental issues			
Start Date	1 st June 2015	Duration	30 months	
Project URL	www.step4youth.eu			
Deliverable	D 7.8 – 3 rd Report on Dissemination Activities			
Work Package	WP 7 - Dissemination			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	30 December 2017	Actual	8 January 2018
Nature	R - Report	Dissemination Level	P – Public	
Lead Beneficiary	PLANO2			
Responsible Authors	Mr. Vassileios Tsekeridis			
Contributions from	All partners			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1	24/11/2017	Draft	1st version of Deliverable	PLANO2
2	12/12/2017	Draft	Update of the existing Deliverable	PLANO2
3	27/12/2017	Draft	Input from pilots added	PLANO2
4	8/01/2018	Final	Submission of final Deliverable	PLANO2

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Table of Contents

1	Executive summary	7
2	Dissemination objectives and expected results	7
3	STEP Dissemination tools	8
3.1	STEP website & Platform.....	8
3.2	Step Platform	9
3.3	STEP Apps.....	10
3.4	STEP blog.....	12
3.5	STEP Turkish Website.....	13
3.6	Social media	14
3.6.1	Facebook pages.....	14
3.6.2	Twitter.....	16
3.6.3	Instagram	19
3.6.4	Flickr account.....	20
3.6.5	YouTube channel	21
3.6.6	Other social media accounts.....	22
3.7	STEP promotional material	22
3.7.1	Audiovisual material.....	22
3.7.2	Newsletters.....	24
3.7.3	Online & Printed Promotional Material	27
4	General dissemination activities performed up to M30	34
4.1	Network of Interest.....	34
4.2	Press Releases & Publications	35
4.3	Person-to-person meetings	40
4.4	Collaboration with similar projects/ initiatives	41
4.5	Participation in studies.....	41
4.6	Participation in events	41
4.7	STEP final event.....	46
5	Pilot partners dissemination activities	47
5.1	Region of Crete (RoC).....	48
5.1.1	Dissemination Events.....	48
5.1.2	Communication with local stakeholders	51
5.2	Mollet del Vallès Municipality (MdV).....	51
5.2.1	Dissemination Events.....	51

5.2.2	Communication with local stakeholders	52
5.3	Valdermoro Municipality	53
5.3.1	Dissemination Events	53
5.3.2	Communication with local stakeholders	57
5.4	Hatay Metropolitan Municipality	59
5.4.1	Dissemination Events	59
5.4.2	Communication with local stakeholders	67
5.5	Association of the Communities of Locride area	68
5.5.1	Dissemination Events	68
5.5.2	Communication with local stakeholders	70
5.6	Resilient Thessaloniki	70
6	Dissemination impact indicators	71
7	Conclusions	72

Table of Figures

Figure 1: STEP website.	8
Figure 2: STEP Platform	9
Figure 3: STEP.green Android application	10
Figure 4: STEP.green iOS application	11
Figure 5: STEP.green App downloads within the Pilot countries	12
Figure 6: STEP blog.....	13
Figure 7. HATAY’s STEP website.....	13
Figure 8.: STEP general Facebook page.....	14
Figure 9: Locride’s pilot Facebook page	15
Figure 10 Hatay’s Facebook Page	15
Figure 11: Valdemoro’s pilot Facebook page.....	15
Figure 12 Pilots Facebook Pages	15
Figure 13. General STEP twitter Account.....	16
Figure 14 STEP general twitter account followers’ characteristics	17
Figure 15 STEP general twitter account followers’ characteristics	18
Figure 16. Locride’s pilot STEP twitter Account	19
Figure 17 RoC’s pilot STEP twitter account	19
Figure 19. Locride’s pilot STEP Instagram account.....	20
Figure 18 Hatay’s pilot STEP instagram account	20
Figure 20RoC’s pilot STEP Instagram account.....	20
Figure 21 Valdemoro’s pilot STEP Instagram account.....	20
Figure 22. Valdemoro’s pilot STEP flickr Account.....	21
Figure 23: STEP YouTube channel	21
Figure 24: STEP YouTube channel	23
Figure 25: Demographics of the STEP video's viewers(a).....	23

Figure 26: Demographics of the STEP video's viewers(b)	23
Figure 27: Demographics of the STEP video's viewers(c).....	24
Figure 28: First page of the 4th Newsletter	24
Figure 29: First page of the 5th Newsletter	25
Figure 30: First page of the 6th Newsletter	25
Figure 31: First page of the 7th Newsletter	26
Figure 32 RoC pilot Newsletter	26
Figure 33: Mollet del Vallès pilot Newsletter	27
Figure 34: Locride’s pilot 2 nd Newsletter	27
Figure 35: Hatay pilot newsletter.....	27
Figure 36: Valdemoro pilot newsletter	27
Figure 37: “17 Sustainable Development Goals” leaflet (side a & side b).....	28
Figure 38: "Tackling Climate Change" leaflet (side a & side b).....	28
Figure 39: "Climate Change", Crete Pilot dialogue (side a & side b)	29
Figure 40: "Urban Social gardens", Thessaloniki pilot area leaflet (side a & side b)	29
Figure 41: "Urban Social gardens", Thessaloniki pilot area poster.....	30
Figure 42: "Climate Change" dialogue, call to action pictures	31
Figure 43: "Air Quality" dialogue, call to action pictures.....	32
Figure 44: STEP final event (promo).....	33
Figure 45: STEP final event (promo).....	33
Figure 46: STEP final event, promo for the STEP pilots.....	34
Figure 47: <i>Study visit “Europe’s Youth as Partners for Sustainable Change”</i>	45
Figure 48: Sziget festival, Yee.....	45
Figure 49: 82nd TIF, DRAXIS.....	46
Figure 50 STEP Final Event	47
Figure 51: Crete dissemination events.....	50
Figure 52: Workshop with students of secondary education and professional education	55
Figure 53: BIKE DAY event.....	55
Figure 54: STEP event- award ceremony	56
Figure 55: World Environment Day event.....	56
Figure 56: Valdemoro, Educating City event.....	57
Figure 57: Technology days at Hatay Iskenderun Technical University – STEP InfoKiosk.....	62
Figure 58: Book Fair - Hatay– STEP InfoKiosk.....	63
Figure 59: Visit to School – STEP	63
Figure 60: Visit to School (b) - STEP	63
Figure 61: Zara Concert – Hatay – STEP	63
Figure 62: Education training center – STEP	64
Figure 63: Mustafa Kemal University’s Graduate party – STEP.....	64
Figure 64: Education training center(b) – STEP.....	64
Figure 65: Open InfoKiosk – STEP	65
Figure 66: Visit to High School – STEP.....	65
Figure 67: Training courses (c) – STEP.....	65
Figure 68: Evvel Temmuz Festival – STEP.....	66
Figure 69: InfoKiosk at Mustafa Kemal University – STEP	66
Figure 70: Training courses (d) - STEP.....	67
Figure 71: InfoKiosk at University (b) – STEP.....	67

Table of Tables

Table 1-STEP website activity.....	9
Table 2- STEP platform activity	10
Table 3 Total Number of downloads of the STEP app.....	11
Table 4 STEP Facebook accounts	15
Table 5 Social Media Accounts promoting STEP	22
Table 6 Means of promoting STEP	35
Table 7 Local Authorities informed about STEP	40
Table 8 Participation in dissemination events.....	41
Table 9RoC Dissemination activities	48
Table 10MdV Dissemination Activities.....	51
Table 11 Valdemoro’s Dissemination Activities	53
Table 12Hatay’s Dissemination Activities.....	59
Table 13 Locride’s Dissemination Activities	68
Table 14 Dissemination Impact Indicators	71

1 Executive summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to report the dissemination activities carried out within the last seven months of the STEP project implementation, i.e. June 2017 – November 2017. In particular, the objectives and expected results of the STEP project are briefly presented (Chapter 2), while the dissemination tools and the dissemination activities performed by partners until M30 (November 2017) are presented in Chapters 4 and 5. Chapter 6 is dedicated to the pilot partners' dissemination activities, and finally, the dissemination impact indicators are presented in Chapter 7.

The major dissemination achievements of the STEP consortium for this year are the following:

- The dissemination of the STEP project has been efficiently implemented through a number of online and offline activities.
- Most of the Dissemination Impact Indicators, initially set, have been achieved, since the project partners have attended/ organised several events in which STEP was presented.
- STEP has been presented to a number of local authorities and most of them found it very attractive and were interested in using it.

2 Dissemination objectives and expected results

The dissemination objectives were defined in detail in deliverable D7.7-2nd Dissemination Plan. According to the deliverable, the main objectives of the STEP dissemination activities were to:

- Raise awareness about the STEP project among youth throughout Europe. Achieve diversity and inclusiveness by involving a demographically balanced group of young people
- Raise awareness of local, regional and national policy makers and public bodies, especially regarding decision-making on environmental issues
- Maximise participation in operations offered by the developed platform / mobile app through the project by drawing the attention of young people using targeted communication means
- Ensure efficient communication and understanding regarding the project, obtain support and encourage participation of all stakeholders, as well as the general public in disseminating information and exploiting results
- Establish formal and informal networks and strengthen and valorise existing ones, for the purpose of exchanging ideas and practices, in order to develop a sense of community by participating in decision making in the fields of the environment and sustainable development and the public sphere in general

Taking into account the dissemination activities performed by all STEP consortium and especially by the pilot partners it is fair to acknowledge that the objectives initially set were achieved. STEP partners managed to raise awareness about the STEP project not only in the pilot areas, but throughout Europe; indubitably, as it was initially foreseen, the activities performed within the pilot areas were more intensive. However, a number of dissemination activities also took place all over Europe, in order to raise awareness on STEP. Additionally, the STEP consortium managed to raise awareness regarding environmental issues and most importantly introduced to the young citizens the concept of participating in the local and Regional decision

making. It should be noted that through the STEP platform 97 dialogues in total brought under public consultation, while almost 10.000 citizens were informed and/or participated in those dialogues.

3 STEP Dissemination tools

The following sections provide an insight in the performance of STEP's dissemination tools that have been prepared for the promotion of the project. Additionally, it presents the new promotional material, which was created after May 2017.

3.1 STEP website & Platform

STEP's website is on air since M3. It is a user- friendly, well- designed and easily accessible website, available at www.step4youth.eu, that was designed taking into account specific provisions and requirements related to the obligations of the EU, gender issues and target groups/stakeholders.

Figure 1: STEP website.

The STEP website consists of the public and private section. The public section presents the project activities and progress, as well as the public deliverables, the dissemination material, the newsletters, etc. The private section is the Member's Area, which was initially created to facilitate the project partners to exchange, upload and download files. However, the project partners decided that it would be more convenient to create a STEP wiki space in order to share documents.

The website activity is monitored using the Google Analytics, a tool that tracks and reports visitor traffic and gives a complete picture of the behaviour of the website audience. The following table briefly presents the data analysis for the STEP website's visits.

Table 1-STEP website activity

Reporting period	June 2015 – May 2016	June 2016 – May 2017	May 2017 – November 2017
Website sessions	1,234	1,934	2,602
Number of website visits	3,863	4,765	5,163
Website users	652	1,224	1,820
Average session duration (period)	4:30	2:38	1:57
Average percentage of new visitors per month	~51,99%	~62,25%	~69.1%
Average percentage of returning visitors per month	~48,01%	~37,8%	~30.9%

One notices that the number of website visits, of users and sessions increased. The rates of new visitors acquired every month (69.1%) reflect the success of the dissemination campaign. The average session duration per user decreased further to 01:57, as a result of the “Call to action” button – “Register & Join STEP” that was added on the website home page (step4youth.eu) , and redirects users directly to the [STEP platform](http://step.green) (step.green),.

3.2 Step Platform

[STEP platform](http://step.green) (step.green), is on air since the beginning of 2017. It is a user- friendly and easily accessible web-platform, also available on App through Google Play Store and Apple iStore, that was designed, taking into account specific provisions and requirements related to the obligations of the EU, gender issues and tested and validated through target groups/stakeholders feedback.

Figure 2: STEP Platform

The STEP Platform activity is monitored using the Google Analytics as well as embedded analytical tools. The following table briefly presents the data analysis for the STEP platform visits.

Table 2- STEP platform activity

Reporting period	May 2017 – November 2017
Number of Platform visits	17,407
Average session duration (period)	5:31
Average percentage of new visitors per month	~52.7%
Average percentage of returning visitors per month	~47.3%

More than half of the users visit the STEP platform directly, 1/3 visits lands on the STEP platform coming from posts on social media and an average of 15% gets redirected from the step4youth website.

3.3 STEP Apps

STEP is also available as mobile application at Google App Store and Apple iStore.

Both Apps, Android and iOS versions, were designed to ensure maximum compatibility, thus the STEP.green application received a 5 star evaluation score (out of 5, only Android Play store provides evaluation scores).

Figure 3: STEP.green Android application

Figure 4: STEP.green iOS application

With regards to applications installations-usability, until end of November, the following user downloads have been performed:

Table 3 Total Number of downloads of the STEP app

Application	No of downloads
STEP.green – Android	1,548
STEP.green – iOS	510
Total	2,058

If we compare the numbers of the table above and the figure below, we notice that the number of downloads of the iOS is exactly the same, while there is a variation in the number of downloads of the Android app. This means that 118 people outside the pilot countries downloaded the Android version of the STEP app. Given the wide reach that the EU pilot dialogues had and the respective promotion actions that were performed, it is expected that some users outside the “pilot countries” have been reached and participated. That engagement of users seems that went further from the STEP platform and partially affected the number of downloads.

Figure 5: STEP.green App downloads within the Pilot countries

3.4 STEP blog

STEP blog went public since the beginning of 2017. YEE has created the blog and is responsible for the blog's content and management.

The blog is available on YEE website, in the ["STEP" section](#)) and the material uploaded concerns articles, news, interviews etc. connected to the topics of STEP project. In more detail publications include among others:

- interviews with people from YEE networks and members of other youth or environmental organisations (e.g. YEE Board Members 2016-2017, members of "Let's do it Macedonia" NGO, "Plastic Soup Foundation", "Voxe.org")
- articles related to the topics of youth participation, e-participation, environmental activism etc.
- articles related to the STEP EU Pilot dialogues
- dissemination articles from YEE's STEP-related events (e.g. participation in Sziget festival)

The blog was managed by YEE's Networking Coordinator (Roxana Nica) with the help of YEE EVS volunteers (Aljaz Malek, Diana Podgurskaia, Cristian Riva, Coline Malot).

The STEP blog has more than 3,500 views coming from Young people either from YEE Member organisations or youths in general that follow the network activities. Furthermore all STEP activities were disseminated also on YEE's social media channels, especially Facebook and Twitter.

Figure 6: STEP blog

3.5 STEP Turkish Website

The STEP Turkish website was created during the first months of the project and all the content is uploaded in Turkish language. This site was created in order to inform Turkish politicians and stakeholders of the Municipality of Hatay about the STEP project. The website can be accessed at the following link Step.hatay.bel.tr and is being fed regularly with news and information about the activities organized by the Municipality of Hatay. The number of visits at the Turkish STEP website is 300.

Figure 7. HATAY's STEP website

3.6 Social media

The general social media accounts for the STEP project were created in Month 2 (PLANO2 was the overall responsible for managing and feeding the general STEP social media accounts), and will be maintained by DRAXIS following the STEP project completion. The aim is to retain an effective way to stay in touch with the STEP target groups, especially with young people, as well as to assist the business exploitation and sustainability of the STEP platform.

During the implementation of the project, most of the STEP pilot partners created additional social media accounts in order to specifically address the needs of their pilot area and reach a critical mass of young people. These accounts were created and managed by the corresponding pilot partner. The Municipality of Mollet del Valles decided to use the already existing accounts in order to promote STEP, since these accounts were quite active and followed by a number of citizens. Additionally, the STEP project was promoted through STEP partners' social media accounts, as well as through the personal accounts of the STEP team members.

3.6.1 Facebook pages

The Facebook page of the STEP project can be found in the following link: <https://www.facebook.com/STEP4youth/>. Easy access to the Facebook page is also provided in each section of the project website as well as in the STEP platform. Otherwise, the page can be found by searching in Facebook for "STEP H2020 Project".

The official language of the page is English. The STEP Facebook page has been created and is managed by PLANO2 and DRAXIS.

Figure 8.: STEP general Facebook page

Facebook is one of the most commonly held social media and most of the pilot partners decided to use it for the dissemination of their pilots' activities, resulting in 4 additional Facebook pages:

- RoC's pilot Facebook page: "@StepRegionCrete" (official language: Greek)
- Locride's pilot Facebook page: "@step h2020 locride" (official language: Italian)
- Valdemoro's pilot Facebook page: "@H2020 STEP Valdemoro" (official language: Spanish)
- Hatay's pilot Facebook page: "@ Step.Green Hatay" (official language: Turkish)

Figure 5: RoC's pilot Facebook page

Figure 9: Locride's pilot Facebook page

Figure 11: Valdemoro's pilot Facebook page

Figure 10 Hatay's Facebook Page

Figure 12 Pilots Facebook Pages

The activity of Facebook pages was monitored using the Facebook Insights which provides information about the page performance, including demographic data about the page audience, and shows how people are discovering and responding to the uploaded posts.

Table 4 STEP Facebook accounts

STEP Facebook page	Number of followers	Reach
General Facebook page	667	41.965
RoC pilot Facebook page	750	47.250
Locride's pilot Facebook page	571	34.153
Valdemoro's pilot Facebook page	84	5.024
Hatay's pilot Facebook page	40	2.392

3.6.2 Twitter

Twitter is the most effective medium-channel when it comes to quick crowdsourcing information. STEP’s general twitter account was used as a primary tool for spreading the project’s news, announcements and dialogues in real time and can be found at the following link: https://twitter.com/STEP_H2020. The name of the STEP Twitter account is “@STEP_H2020”, while the preferred hashtag for the project tweets is “#STEP_H2020”. Tweets were uploaded in a regular base and they referred to general information about youth STEP news and events. The STEP Twitter account was a useful channel to inform and engage with its target audiences.

Figure 13. General STEP twitter Account

The number of followers of the STEP general twitter account is 245, while the STEP general twitter account managed to successfully reach a substantial amount of users achieving a significant number of 10.174 impressions.

The STEP general twitter account, STEP_H2020, followers present some very valuable characteristics and showcase a strong mix of interests:

Figure 14 STEP general twitter account followers' characteristics

Furthermore, a comparison between STEP twitter followers and Twitter audience group "Millennials" (users aged 18-34) showcases a sturdy base of followers:

Figure 15 STEP general twitter account followers' characteristics

Locride and Region of Crete have also created a twitter account for the promotion of STEP. The name of Locride's account is "@steplocride" and can be found at the following link: <https://twitter.com/steplocride>, while the name of RoC's account is @STEP_Crete and can be found at the link below: http://twitter.com/STEP_Crete. However, the pilot partners decided that Facebook is more effective for the dissemination of STEP so these accounts have not been actively used by the pilot partners. The number of followers is 20 for Locride's account and 13 for RoC's.

Figure 16. Locride’s pilot STEP twitter Account

Figure 17 RoC’s pilot STEP twitter account

3.6.3 Instagram

Instagram is a quite widespread social media and its popularity has been growing steadily, especially in younger ages. For this reason, four STEP pilots, Hatay, Locride Valdemorero and recently RoC decided to create an account on Instagram. The names of the Instagram accounts are:

- Hatay’s account: “step.greenhatay” with 2,287 followers
- Locride’s account: “steph2020locride” with 232 followers
- Valdemorero’s account: “stepvaldemoro” with 56 followers
- RoC’s account: “stepregioncrete” with 28 followers

Figure 18 Hatay's pilot STEP instagram account

Figure 19. Locride's pilot STEP Instagram account

Figure 21 Valdemoro's pilot STEP Instagram account

Figure 20RoC's pilot STEP Instagram account

3.6.4 Flickr account

Flickr is an online photo management and sharing application, that attracts the interest of a number of people. The pilot of Valdemoro decided to create a STEP account in this social media in order to present the activities performed by the Municipality concerning STEP. Flickr is also integrated with Facebook, so it is easier for the Municipality of Valdemoro to share the uploaded content with the respective facebook account. Even though there are no followers in Valdemoro's flickr account, it should be noted that it counts 1,871 visits.

Figure 22. Valdemoro's pilot STEP flickr Account

3.6.5 YouTube channel

The creation of audio-visual material for the promotion of the STEP project was of crucial importance as such tools are more attractive to young people. A YouTube channel had been created for the STEP project, under the name "STEP Horizon2020" and is available at <https://goo.gl/SkfgkJ>.

Figure 23: STEP YouTube channel

12 videos had been uploaded on the STEP channel and one playlist, having a total of 1.315 views. More specifically, STEP channel contains:

- STEP's promotional video in 6 languages, which provides general information about the project and addresses young people.
- 6 videos that provide information about STEP social media monitoring tool and its use.

3.6.6 Other social media accounts

The STEP project and the activities organized in its framework were promoted through the partners already existing social media accounts. More particularly, STEP and especially the EU pilot was intensively promoted by YEE through its Facebook and twitter account. YEE Facebook page currently has over 4,200 likes (data collected in December 2017). The average reach for STEP-related posts is 600 people. The average number of clicks/actions is 19. The YEE Twitter page currently has 200 followers (data collected in December 2017).

STEP was also promoted through additional social media accounts managed by the local pilots. These accounts contributed to the effective dissemination of the project, since they already had a critical mass of engaged followers. The table below presents the accounts per pilot partner, as well as the followers of each account.

Table 5 Social Media Accounts promoting STEP

Pilot	Social Media accounts	No of Followers
MdV	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/ajuntamentmollet	2,165
	Twitter: https://twitter.com/ajmollet/	3,843
	Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/ViuMollet	331
Valdemoro	Facebook: Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro	3,209
	twitter: Ayuntamiento de Valdemoro	2,531
	FLICKR: Valdemoro	31
Hatay	Instagram : expohatay2021	230
	instagram.com/hataysocial	11,200
	Instagram: hataybsb	8,061
	Facebook.com/HatayBld	48,944
	Twitter.com/HatayBSB	5,000
	instagram: aegeehatay	330
	instagram: ejderyadergi	14,400
	twitter.com/genctema_hatay	2,500
	instagram: mkugenctema	1,701
	instagram: expo2021.hatay	294
Facebook: LutfuSavas (Mayor)	139,741	

3.7 STEP promotional material

3.7.1 Audiovisual material

STEP pilots uploaded STEP's video on their social media accounts, webpages and presented it at their local Civil Service Centers, schools, fairs, events, etc.

Figure 24: STEP YouTube channel

In the following screens, information from the YouTube analytics is briefly presented. The time of these analytics is from the beginning of the project until the end of November 2017.

Figure 25: Demographics of the STEP video's viewers(a)

Figure 26: Demographics of the STEP video's viewers(b)

Regarding the demographics of viewers of STEP videos, 52% of them are men and 48% women, while the majority of the audience belonging to the 25-34 age group, i.e. part of the target group of the project (i.e 18-30-year-old).

Viewer gender ↑	Watch time (minutes) Ⓞ	13-17	18-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	65+
Female	48%	0.0%	10%	43%	26%	16%	3.8%	0.7%
Male	52%	1.1%	8.9%	68%	13%	4.9%	0.8%	3.4%

Figure 27: Demographics of the STEP video's viewers(c)

3.7.2 Newsletters

From June 2017 (M25) until November 2017 (M30) four newsletters were issued to inform all stakeholders about project news-progress and dialogues as well as to call them to action and engage them and their networks within the STEP dialogues.

The **first** one was sent at the beginning of July 2017 (M26). The topics addressed in that issue were:

- The concept of the STEP project
- The concept of the STEP platform
- A brief presentation and call to action for the EU pilot dialogue on the “17 Sustainable Development Goals”

Figure 28: First page of the 4th Newsletter

The next newsletter was sent at the beginning of September 2017 (M28). Topics included in that newsletter were:

- The concept of the STEP platform
- An introduction to STEP pilots
- A brief presentation and call to action for the EU pilot dialogue on Climate Change!

Figure 29: First page of the 5th Newsletter

The third newsletter was sent at the beginning of September 2017 (M28). Topics included in that newsletter were:

- The concept of the STEP platform
- An introduction to STEP pilots
- A brief presentation and call to action for the EU pilot dialogue on Air Quality!

Figure 30: First page of the 6th Newsletter

The fourth newsletter was sent at the beginning of September 2017 (M28). Topics included in that newsletter were:

- The concept of the STEP platform
- An introduction to STEP pilots
- A brief presentation and call to action for the EU pilot dialogue on Air Quality!
- An announce and introduction of the STEP eParticipation Working group!
- An announcement for the STEP Final Event

Figure 31: First page of the 7th Newsletter

An additional has been prepared and will be sent at the beginning of January 2018. Topics included in that newsletter were:

- Lessons learned from the STEP local pilots
- The experience of the STEP final event
- Results from the EU dialogues

All the above five newsletters are in English and they have been/will be shared with the STEP Network of Interest (NoI) members a total of 2.712 members. Additionally, all newsletters were uploaded on the project website and they were also sent to STEP partners so that they may distribute them via their communication channels.

Furthermore, all pilot partners prepared and circulated a number of Newsletters in their mother language. All pilot newsletters were formatted similarly, containing information about the project, the pilot dialogues progress, the dialogues that witnessed the higher participation as well as currently open or to be opened dialogues.

Figure 32 RoC pilot Newsletter

Figure 33: Mollet del Vallès pilot Newsletter

Figure 34: Locride's pilot 2nd Newsletter

Figure 35: Hatay pilot newsletter

Figure 36: Valdemoro pilot newsletter

3.7.3 Online & Printed Promotional Material

A number of printed dissemination material was created during those months to support the STEP actions and inform youths and stakeholders of its activities. This material was also promoted through the web and the various social media accounts. More specifically:

A leaflet was created to be distributed by partner Yee in the Sziget festival (August 8th-15th 2017) and support the EU pilot dialogue on the topic of the “17 Sustainable Development Goals”.

Figure 37: "17 Sustainable Development Goals" leaflet (side a & side b)

Another leaflet was created to support the EU pilot dialogue on the topic of the "Tackling Climate Change".

Figure 38: "Tackling Climate Change" leaflet (side a & side b).

A variation of the aforementioned leaflet was created to support the Crete pilot dialogue on the topic of the "Climate Change", a dialogue where participation was awarded with the attendance of 2 youths in the STEP final event.

Figure 39: "Climate Change", Crete Pilot dialogue (side a & side b)

Another leaflet that was created and distributed to the local area of Thessaloniki, was formatted to support the dialogue of "Urban Social gardens". The leaflet was distributed in central spots of the city. A poster was also formatted for the same reason, given that the participation to this dialogue was giving the opportunity to two lucky youths, following a draw, to attend the STEP final event.

Figure 40: "Urban Social gardens", Thessaloniki pilot area leaflet (side a & side b)

Figure 41: "Urban Social gardens", Thessaloniki pilot area poster

Additionally, the pilot of Locride designed and printed 7.500 stickers, which were promoted through the various dissemination activities organized within the pilot area.

Furthermore, a series of "call to actions" graphics were designed and used to engage Youths and participants to the EU pilot. The banners presented below were used for posts at STEP's the social media accounts.

D7.8: 3rd Report on Dissemination Activities

Figure 42: "Climate Change" dialogue, call to action pictures

D7.8: 3rd Report on Dissemination Activities

Figure 43: "Air Quality" dialogue, call to action pictures

Additional promotional material was designed especially for the dissemination needs of STEP’s final event in Berlin. This material was distributed through STEP general social media accounts, as well as through the accounts of the pilots and the rest of the partners.

Figure 44: STEP final event (promo)

Figure 45: STEP final event (promo)

Figure 46: STEP final event, promo for the STEP pilots

4 General dissemination activities performed up to M30

The following sections outline the general dissemination activities that were carried out in the period June 2017 – November 2017 (M25- M30) by all project partners.

4.1 Network of Interest

The establishment and maintenance of the STEP Network of Interest (NoI) was an ongoing process that spanned throughout the entire lifetime of the STEP project. STEP NoI is well-established and today counts more than 2.710 members from all over the world. The NoI members derived from four sources:

- a) extensive search through the Internet
- b) network of each partner
- c) b2b meetings with stakeholders during partners' participation in events
- d) stakeholders subscribed to the STEP newsletter.

A number of online and offline activities have been implemented in order to maintain the network, keep its members updated on STEP's news and enrich it with additional stakeholders; all these activities are described in detail in D7.9 – 3rd Network of Interest.

4.2 Press Releases & Publications

A number of press releases have been sent from STEP pilot partners in order to disseminate the project activities and the dialogues that each pilot uploaded on the platform. Additionally, the partners gave interviews at local TV stations and radios in order to present STEP and the running / upcoming dialogues. The table below presents relevant press releases:

Table 6 Means of promoting STEP

Partner	Topic	URL / type of media	Date
ROC	Environment and e-Participation	http://www.goodnet.gr/rethymno.html/ ...	20/10/2017
ROC	Region of Crete – Press release		10/11/2017
ROC	Region of Crete – Press release		29/09/2017
ROC	Region of Crete – Press release		17/05/2017
ROC	Presenting STEP project to EU educators	http://hania.news/2017/11/10/%CF%80%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%85%CF%83%CE%AF%CE%B1%CF%83%CE%B7-%CE%B5%CF%85%CF%81%CF%89%CF%80%CE%B1%CF%8A%CE%BA%CF%8E%CE%BD-	10/11/2017

D7.8: 3rd Report on Dissemination Activities

		http://www.candianews.gr/2017/11/10/xenikathigites-stin-periferia-kritis-stin-parousiasi-perivallontikon-draseon/	
ROC	Themis Natura Event	http://www.ert.gr/%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%B1%CE%BE%CE%B9%CE%BD%CF%8C%CE%BC%CE%B7%CF%84%CE%B1/periferia-kritis-sto-ethniko-synedrio-giati-perivallontiki-efthyni/	8-10/09/2017
ROC	STEP press release	http://www.lifethemis.eu/el/eldcongress/announcements/986	14/09/2017
ROC	STEP press release	Flashnews	19/05/2017
ROC	STEP press release	CNA news	17/05/2017
ROC	STEP press release	ekriti.gr cretalive.gr	17/05/2017
ROC	STEP press release	http://www.zarpanews.gr/%CF%87%CE%B1%CE%BD%CE%B9%CE%AC-%CF%80%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%85%CF%83%CE%AF%CE%B1%CF%83%CE%B7-%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%85-%CF%80%CF%81%CE%BF%CE%B3%CF%81%CE%AC%CE%BC%CE%BC%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%82-step/ http://flashnews.gr/post/312487/paroyysiash-ths-platformas-step-sto-polytexneio-krhths http://tuc.gr http://hania.news http://palo.gr http://tourismtoday.gr	22/05/2017
ROC	Radio interview	Team Fm 102.0 station	07/2017
ROC	Articles at local daily newspapers	Haniotika nea Kritiki epitheorisi Patris Anatoli Rethimniotika nea	Various dates
MDV	STEP press release at Newspapers and TV	Newspaper articles about the “Antirumors” dialogue - 2 articles in 4 cantons -1 article at Mollet a mà - 2 articles in Municipal website - Local TV, vallès Visió	May 2017
MDV	STEP press release at Newspapers and TV	Newspaper and online articles about the dialogues: “Local Plan for Young People experiences and activities” & “What would you improve from Citizens Attention Office” - 2 Articles in Mollet a mà - 4 entries at the municipal webpage - 1 article in Contrapunt - 1 article in 4 Cantons - Several entries at the webpage for young people	October 2017

D7.8: 3rd Report on Dissemination Activities

MDV	STEP press release at Newspapers and TV	Newspaper articles about the dialogues: “Share the Summer City Festival” & “Winners of the dialogue Share the Summer City festival”. -1 article in Contrapunt -1 article in 4 Cantons -3 articles in the Municipal website	August 2017
MDV	STEP press release at Newspapers and TV	Newspaper article about the dialogue “Winners of the dialogue_Artisans Fair_Do you like it” - 1 article in Contrapunt -1 article in 4 Cantons -2 article in Mollet a mà -2 entries in the municipal webpage -Local TV 1 entry	September 2017
MDV	STEP press release at Newspapers and TV	Newspaper and online articles about the dialogue “Choose the initiatives projects that you like the most”: - 2 articles in the municipal webpage - 2 entries in the website for young people -3 articles in Mollet a Mà (paper article) -3 articles in Contrapunt (paper article) - 1 article in 4 cantons - 2 entries in the Local TV (Valles Visió)	September 2017
MDV	STEP press release at Newspapers and TV	Newspaper and online articles about the dialogue “Artisans Fair. Do you like it” - 1 article in Contrapunt (local newspaper) - 1 article in 4 Cantons (local newspaper) - 2 articles in Mollet a mà - 2 entries in the municipal webpage -Local TV 1 entry	September 2017
MDV	STEP press release at Newspapers and TV	Newspaper and online articles about the dialogue “City Council” - 1 article in Mollet a mà - 1 article in 4 Cantons - 1 entry in the website	July 2017
MDV	STEP press release at Newspapers and TV	Newspaper and online articles about the dialogue “Decide and Allocate 100.000 euros” -1 article at the website -1 article in 4 cantons -1 article in Contrapunt -1 article in Mollet a mà	July 2017
MDV	STEP press release at Newspapers and TV	Results of the participative meeting for the Waste Prevention Municipal Plan -1 article in Contrapunt -1 entry in the Local TV	September 2017
VLD	Promotion of final event	https://www.facebook.com/valdemoronews/videos/1745783822129764/	07/11/2017
Locride	Promotional Video for STEP	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_jmr4lIdRiU	11/05/2017
Locride	Promotion of STEP meeting	http://www.citynow.it/calabria-si-incontra-leuropa-un-meeting-internazionale/	27/05/2017

		<p>https://corrierelocride.it/eventi-ia/l-europa-si-incontra-nella-locride-grazie-a-step http://www.ecodellalocride.it/news/leuropa-si-incontra-nella-locride-grazie-a-step/ http://ildispaccio.it/agora/39-reggio-calabria/145915-l-europa-si-incontra-nella-locride-grazie-a-step http://www.lentelocale.it/home/il-progetto-leuropa-si-incontra-nella-locride-grazie-a-step/ http://www.telemia.it/2017/05/locride-step-giovani-parte-attiva-dei-processi-decisionali/ http://www.veritasnews24.it/index.php?option=com_k2&view=item&id=22791:siderno-rc-progetto-europeo-step-programma-horizon-2020-meeting-internazionale-in-calabria&highlight=WyJwcm9nZXR0byIsInNOZXAiLCJwcm9nZXR0byBzdGVwIlO</p>	
Locride	Promotion of STEP project and treasure hunt in Locride	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - http://www.citynow.it/la-storia-giovani-step-green-speciale-caccia-al-tesoro-locri/ - https://corrierelocride.it/giovani/la-storia-i-giovani-e-step-green-speciale-caccia-al-tesoro-a-locri - http://www.ecodellalocride.it/news/santagata-del-bianco-rc-la-storia-i-giovani-e-step-green-speciale-caccia-al-tesoro-a-locri/ - http://ildispaccio.it/agora/39-reggio-calabria/155036-il-31-agosto-speciale-caccia-al-tesoro-locri-tra-storia-e-leggenda - http://www.telemia.it/2017/08/santagata-del-bianco-rc-la-storia-giovani-step-green-speciale-caccia-al-tesoro-locri/ 	30/08/2017
Locride	Promotion of STEP project and treasure hunt info in Locride	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - http://www.citynow.it/step-attivita-allaperto-dialoghi-digitali-step-green-progetto-europeo-si-afferma-nel-mondo-giovanile/ - https://corrierelocride.it/societa/step-attivita-allaperto-e-dialoghi-digitali-su-step-green-il-progetto-europeo-si-afferma-nel-mondo-giovanile - http://www.ecodellalocride.it/news/locride-rc-stepil-progetto-europeo-si-afferma-nel-mondo-giovanile/ - http://ildispaccio.it/reggio-calabria/156184-successo-per-step-green-nella-locride - http://www.lentelocale.it/home/step-attivita-allaperto-e-dialoghi-digitali-un-progetto-europeo-che-si-afferma-nel-mondo-giovanile/ - http://www.telemia.it/2017/09/locride-rc-stepil- 	12/09/2017

		progetto-europeo-si-afferma-nel-mondo-giovanile/ http://www.zoomsud.it/index.php/flash-news/99793-locri-rc-successo-per-la-caccia-al-tesoro-organizzata-da-step-e-da-civitas-solis	
DRAXIS	Press Release	<p>- http://www.zougla.gr/technology/world-of-tech/article/step-h-nea-efarmogi-gia-ti-simetoxiton-neon-stis-diadikasies-lipsis-apofaseon</p> <p>https://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=2&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0ahUKEwif6NHAKsHYAhWSpKQKHSn DcsQFggsMAE&url=http%3A%2F%2Fpress724.gr%2Fstep-h-%25CE%25BD%25CE%25AD%25CE%25B1-%25CE%25B5%25CF%2586%25CE%25B1%25CF%2581%25CE%25BC%25CE%25BF%25CE%25B3%25CE%25AE-%25CE%25B3%25CE%25B9%25CE%25B1-%25CF%2584%25CE%25B7-%25CF%2583%25CF%2585%25CE%25BC%25CE%25BC%25CE%25B5%25CF%2584%25CE%25BF%25CF%2587%25CE%25AE-%25CF%2584%25CF%2589%25CE%25BD-%25CE%25BD%25CE%25AD%25CF%2589%2F&usg=AOvVaw1PhPclV5EBdzKdal-DEJNw</p> <p>https://www.typologos.com/step-h-%CE%BD%CE%B5%CE%B1-%CE%B5%CF%86%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%BC%CE%BF%CE%B3%CE%B7-%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%B1-%CF%84%CE%B7-%CF%83%CF%85%CE%BC%CE%BC%CE%B5%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%87%CE%B7-%CF%84%CF%89%CE%BD-%CE%BD%CE%B5%CF%89/</p>	September 2017
DRAXIS	Press Release	http://www.epixeiro.gr/article/66672	26/10/2017

Apart from the publications in the local and national press, a scientific paper was published in the framework of the 4th Internet Science Conference INSCI conference 2017. The paper was also published on Springer. The Conference took place in November 2017 in Greece and DRAXIS was responsible for the preparation, as well as the presentation of the paper, while CERTH, Sampas and Abertay provided input. Additionally, acknowledgements to STEP have been in two scientific papers that were prepared by CERTH:

- “Open-Source Monitoring, Search and Analytics Over Social Media”, presented at the International Conference on Internet Science, available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-70284-1_28
- “Tunable Plug-In Rules with Reduced Posterior Certainty Loss in Imbalanced Datasets”, presented at the First International Workshop on Learning with Imbalanced Domains: Theory and Applications, available at: <http://proceedings.mlr.press/v74/krasanakis17a.html>

4.3 Person-to-person meetings

A number of meetings have taken place for effective dissemination and full valorisation of the STEP platform. The STEP partners have organised meetings with representatives of local authorities in their area in order to present STEP. During these meetings the representatives of the STEP team presented the objectives of the project and demonstrated the platform. The table below indicates the local authorities that have been informed about STEP in the framework of a workshop, an event, or during a b2b meeting. All the Municipalities below provided positive feedback and they are generally interested in using STEP, but they need additional time, since engaging citizens in digital participation is a quite time-consuming process and demands a lot of human resources.

Table 7 Local Authorities informed about STEP

Country	Name of the Authority
Italy	Municipality of Siderno (main city in the Locride areas) Metropolitan city of Reggio Calabria Aspromonte National Park Municipality of Bologna Municipality of Florence Municipality of Genoa Municipality of Turin
Spain	Ajuntament de Badalona Ajuntament de Barberà del Vallès Ajuntament de Cerdanyola del Vallès Ajuntament de Girona Ajuntament de Granollers Ajuntament de Mataró Ajuntament de Prat del Llobregat Ajuntament de Rubí Ajuntament de Sabadell Ajuntament de Santa coloma de Gramanet Ajuntament de Terrassa Ajuntament de Vic Balearic Islands Municipality Lucena Municipality
Greece	Municipality of Amaroussion Municipality of Athens
Turkey	Samandağ Municipality Defne Municipality Besiktas Municipality Bursa Municipality Istanbul Municipality Izmir Municipality

4.4 Collaboration with similar projects/ initiatives

Since the beginning of the project the STEP consortium attempted to create synergies with similar projects and initiatives in order to exchange valuable information, experience and to further collaborate with them. It should be noted that the STEP consortia has created a quite strong collaboration with the [EUth](#) project. Mrs Kerstin Franzl, the coordinator of the [EUth](#), is a member of the STEP Advisory Board. In this framework the STEP consortium decided to organize STEP final event within the EUth final Conference. Additional information about STEP final event is provided in the relevant [Chapter 4.7](#).

4.5 Participation in studies

The STEP team is always eager to participate in studies and initiatives that will enhance the dissemination of the project. Until May 2017, the STEP team had already participated in two studies, while since June 2017, the STEP team provided input for the study below:

“Study on the Impact of the Internet and Social Media on Youth Participation and Youth Work”. The overall objective of the study was to examine how the internet and social media influence young people’s active citizenship and political participation and how those working with them, particularly youth workers, can use internet and social media based tools to engage with all young people, including disadvantaged groups, in an effective and meaningful way. As part of the study an inventory of good practices on innovative and creative ways to utilise the internet and social media, including digital tools and apps aimed at participation would be established. The STEP team accepted the invitation and participated in an interview with the persons in charge of the study.

4.6 Participation in events

The table below presents the events that the STEP partners have participated in, in order to promote the STEP project and create synergies with other stakeholders from various countries. The events that STEP pilots have participated / organized are presented in the respective [Pilots Chapter](#).

Table 8 Participation in dissemination events

Partner	Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
DRAXIS	4 th International Conference on Internet Science – INSCI 2017	The INSCI aims at progressing and investigating on topics of high relevance with Internet’s impact on society, governance, and innovation. It focuses on the contribution and role of Internet science on the current and future multidisciplinary understanding of societies transformations, governance shifts and innovation quests. Its main objective is to allow an open and productive dialogue between all the disciplines which study the Internet as a socio-technical system under any	~100	22-24/11/2017

		technological or humanistic perspectives. The STEP project was presented during the 2 nd day of the Conference at the session “Politics & Public Co-Creation in the Internet”.		
YEE	Study visit “Europe's Youth as Partners for Sustainable Change”	The aim of the study was to gain a better understanding of the implementation of the EU’s climate change goals from a local and regional perspective and share their opinion on how young people can be better involved in promoting a positive European narrative. It was also an opportunity to enhance STEP project awareness, communicate project outcomes, encourage involvement, strengthen links with public bodies, help with possible exploitation position, etc.	>40	22-23/11/2017
DRAXIS	Presentation of STEP at Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	In October, DRAXIS team visited the School of Agriculture of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, in order to present the STEP platform and invite the students to participate in Thessaloniki’s pilot open dialogue about the urban gardens.		
YEE	Seminar on Youth Participation in Internet Governance <i>European Youth Centre Strasbourg, France</i>	The seminar was exploring how youth participation in Internet Governance can be ensured in a meaningful and inclusive manner and was formulated recommendations for future action to be taken by the Youth Department and the Council of Europe to support youth participation. Objectives: 1. To map together with the participants the Internet Governance process and stakeholders, and the position of young people within it 2. To develop a shared understanding of youth participation in Internet governance and analyse the achievements and pitfall of current youth participation in these processes 3. To further explore what are the rights, the means, the spaces, the opportunities and the support required by young people in order to meaningfully participate in the shaping of the Internet 4. To review the objectives for youth	>35	24-26/10/2017

		<p>participation in Internet Governance and identify the role and contribution of youth organisations and other stakeholders towards these</p> <p>5. To elaborate policy and programme recommendations for the Youth Department and the Council of Europe that aim to support and enhance youth participation in Internet Governance.</p> <p>After the seminar Yee members attending the event, created a Google group and a Facebook group and utilized these channels to share step project news and the new Air Quality dialogue.</p>		
	<p>“ICT-enabled open government and public sector innovation through digital solutions” & “Digital Transformation of Public Administrations & Project Cluster Event on Sustainability and Exploitation of Project Results”</p>	<p>Two linked events were organized in a two-day event in October 2017 targeting Open Government actions in H2020 in order to foster the exploitation of research and innovation results and the post project continuity from operational and policy stances. The main goal of the event was to create a friendly environment for interaction and clustering between EU projects. Additionally, presentations took place on the sustainability of eGovernment activities and sharing exploitation practices and challenges for a cluster of H2020 eGovernment projects. The STEP team met partners from other relevant projects and exchanged information on issues relevant to the exploitation of the projects’ results.</p>	80	23-24/10/2017
DRAXIS	<p>Eu Project Workshop</p>	<p>The “Eu Project Workshop” on gamification, environmental awareness, sensor networks, social inclusion and education issues took place in Athens and apart from STEP another four European projects were presented. The STEP team discussed with the rest of the participants possible ways of collaboration.</p>	~40	18/10/2017
DRAXIS	<p>82nd Thessaloniki International Fair - TIF</p>	<p>TIF is the largest fair organized in Greece and the STEP team was there for the second consecutive year. This year 263,724 individuals went through the gates of the Fair from 9 to 17 September and visited the largest TIF of the last decade the STEP project. All the 5 days of the fair the STEP team was hosted at the</p>	<40.000	9-13/09/2017

		Organic Products Cluster stand and promoted the STEP platform and invited the citizens to participate at EU pilot's and the Resilient Thessaloniki's open dialogues.		
YEE	Sziget festival, Tent at NGO Island,	<p>The aim of the YEE representation at the NGO Island was to inform young people about the STEP project, engage them in using the STEP platform and involving them in activities related to e.g. youth participation and e-participation in sustainable development and environmental issues.</p> <p>Participation in this event was connected to the STEP objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -To enable young citizens to participate in decision-making on issues with environmental impact – By having young people using the step.green platform and mobile app -To ensure appropriate dissemination of project activities and results – By promoting the project and the STEP platform <p>Create awareness about the project's outcomes, encourage involvement, create synergies with organisations or projects (we got in contact with the Board of Climate-KIC organisation who were present for one day at the event as well and spoke about the project & platform)</p>	>1200	9-15/08/2017

Figure 47: Study visit “Europe's Youth as Partners for Sustainable Change”

Figure 48: Sziget festival, Yee

Figure 49: 82nd TIF, DRAXIS

4.7 STEP final event

STEP final event was organized on 8/12/2017 within the EUth Open Summit “Youth eParticipation in Europe: The Future is now”, which took place on 7-8 /12/2017 in Berlin. During all the 30 months of the project implementation, the STEP team was in close cooperation with the EUth project, so in order to exploit synergies the STEP partners decided to organize STEP’s final event in parallel with EUth’s final conference. For this purpose the STEP team requested one month extension for the STEP project. On this occasion over 140 youth eParticipation practitioners, researchers, developers, policy-makers and young people from all over Europe got together to discuss the future of youth eParticipation.

The main goal of the final event was the STEP team to present the experience gained, to demonstrate the final version of the STEP platform and to discuss the results generated from 30 months’ work.

Additionally, in order to award active youth participation, each STEP pilot implemented a contest through the STEP platform giving as a unique prize a trip for two young people to Berlin in order to participate in STEP’s final event. In this framework 13 young citizens coming from the STEP pilot areas joined STEP final event and elaborated on their experience, ideas and perceived value of eParticipation! The feedback received about the STEP platform by the young winners of the contest was quite positive, while it should be noted that most of the winners were informed about the STEP platform through the internet.

The discussion that followed the presentations was around the questions: How to enable more youth eParticipation? What can public authorities gain from enabling youths participation? What is Youths perceived value of eParticipation? The main result of the discussion pointed out that digital tools are important, but the participatory process and the participatory culture are basic to inspire citizens’ participation. Policy makers should understand the power of a participatory process and invest in digital tools in order to build on the participatory culture. A convincing message to the young citizens is quite important, while the engagement of young people who will act as a poll and support the dissemination of the public dialogues to their peers is also necessary.

For the STEP team, the final event was not an ending point on the contrary it was the starting point, for new initiatives and more active youth citizenship enablers.

Figure 50 STEP Final Event

5 Pilot partners dissemination activities

The Deliverable 7.7, 2nd Dissemination plan, presents the local dissemination plan of the STEP pilots. Pilot partners followed the general framework of this deliverable and adjusted it according to their special needs and the timeframe that was more convenient to them. According to D 7.7, each STEP pilot partner had to establish a core group of users and organize a workshop with them in order to discuss possible methods of engaging young people in STEP and local events. Moreover, when the STEP platform would be ready, each pilot partner would organise one launch event. All these activities were implemented until March 2017 and have already been reported in D 7.5, 2nd Report on Dissemination Activities. Since the beginning of the open pilot, each pilot partner organized a number of activities to promote the STEP platform to young citizens, disseminate the public dialogues and achieve participation of young people. This chapter presents the

dissemination activities and the events each pilot partner organized/participated in. The reported period is from May 2017 – November 2017. Most of the dissemination activities implemented in May were reported in the previous deliverable D 7.5, 2nd Report on Dissemination Activities. However, there are some activities that weren't reported in the previous period and are presented in this one.

5.1 Region of Crete (RoC)

The RoC developed a quite intensive communication strategy in order to promote the STEP project to young citizens and encourage them to participate in decision making procedures. Such strategies included the use of social media and especially Facebook, the establishment of synergies with environmental and youth associations, as well as the systematic use of online invitations, sent through the STEP platform. Apart from the extensive presence in social media and local mass media RoC STEP team showed great commitment and willingness to the offline promotion of the STEP platform as well. In this context the Region of Crete has presented STEP to a number of local and national events organized in different cities of Crete.

5.1.1 Dissemination Events

The dissemination activities of Crete's pilot are briefly presented below.

Table 9RoC Dissemination activities

Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
8 th p_public Festival	The event was organized by the p_public team, formed by young architects, in order to activate general public about the accessibility to public space and the need of viable cities. STEP presentation in the event aimed to increase awareness of young people about the project and call them to participate in environmental issue dialogues of the Region of Crete.	>200	10 -11/6/2017
Erasmus+/Action KA2 "GO FOR CONTENT LANGUAGE AND INTEGRATED LEARNING	The event was organized within the project Erasmus+/Action KA2 "GO FOR CONTENT LANGUAGE AND INTEGRATED LEARNING. The event aim was to present innovation tools and good practices for environmental education to a group of European teachers and representatives of Cretan Schools and Education authorities. STEP project as well as other environmental projects were presented to local and European education representatives. Following the STEP project presentation, a demonstration of the platform took place. The possibility of capitalizing upon the STEP platform in education, was discussed and exploited.	24	10/11/2017
Technological Institute of Crete, Chania	The event was organized by the Technological Institute of Crete, the Department of Natural Sources and Environment at their Campus, located at Chania. The event was also open to all students of the Schools located at Chania. STEP project was extensively presented as well as the	>159	2/11/2017

D7.8: 3rd Report on Dissemination Activities

	platform and the active dialogues. Youths were invited to register and participate in the Climate Change dialogue		
Event at the University of Crete	The event was organized by the Public Relationship Department of the University of Crete, at their Campus, located at Rethymno. The event was open to all students of the Schools located at Rethymno, which are among other the School of Social Sciences (Department of Sociology, Department of Political Science, Department of Economics, etc) School of Philosophy etc and intended to present the STEP project, the platform and active dialogues to the students. Youths were invited to register and participate in the Climate Change dialogue.	>2,500	18/10/2017
Welcome Event for the First year Students of the Technical University of Crete (TUC)	The event was organized by the Public Relationship Department of the Technical University of Crete. The event attendees all first year students of the Technical University (Schools of Environmental Engineering, Architecture, etc). STEP participated to the event and performed an extensive presentation of the project activities and platform to the attendees. Youths had the opportunity to have a hands-on experience of the platform and more specifically of the Climate Change dialogues, during the event.	>500	27/9/2017
National Conference of Greek Botanical company, MAICH	STEP participated to the event and performed an extensive presentation of the project activities and platform to the attendees. The majority of the audience were Young scientists (biologists etc.) of Greece dealing with environmental issues and biodiversity. It was a great opportunity to raise awareness about the STEP project as well as to present and engage youths in the STEP platform.	>100	14-17/9/2017
“Environmental responsibility, prevention and reclamation”, Heraklion	STEP project participated to this event and performed an extensive presentation of the project activities and platform to the attendees. The conference was open to public and given the scope of the conference, general awareness for environmental crimes, an appropriate and receptive audience had attended.	>125	8-10/9/2017
August Agricultural Exhibition, Chania	The festival was organized by the Regional Unit of Chania, the Municipality of Chania and the Chania Chamber of Commerce. The event intended to promote Cretan products and activities to local people and visitors. The Region of Crete maintained a kiosk with informative material (flyers, banner, video) about their Crete STEP Pilot activities, dialogues etc.	>2,000	25-31/08/2017
Cretan Diet Festival	The festival was organized by the Regional Unit of Rethymno, the Municipality of Rethymno and the Rethymno Chamber of Commerce and intends to promote Cretan products, art and activities to local people and visitors. During the festival the Region of Crete maintained a kiosk with information material	>2,000	1-7/07/2017

	(flyers) about our actions and projects among them STEP. Information material about the STEP project, its scope and information about its local pilot implementation was provided to public. Due to parallel events (music etc) the festival is very popular (more than 10.000 participants during the seven days), so it had a significant impact for increasing awareness about the project.		
Rethymnon, Chamber of Commerce and Industry Event	The event was organized by the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Rethymnon. The purpose of the STEP presentation to the event was to inform the audience about the STEP project and platform, to establish synergies with the Lawyer’s Associations of Rethymnon and Chania, encourage involvement of young scientists (lawyers and engineers) to environmental matters, to increase awareness creation about the availability to express young people’s views about environmental matters to the authorities.	>50	9/6/2017
Event at the Technical University of Crete	The event was organized by the Public Relationship Department of the Technical University of Crete, at their Campus. The event was open to all students of the Technical University and intended to present the STEP project and the STEP platform to the students. Following the presentation an email containing information about the STEP project and platform was send to the participants and the Technical University of Crete students.	>6,500	24/5/2017

Figure 51: Crete dissemination events

5.1.2 Communication with local stakeholders

The pilot -testing period provided the opportunity for the RoC to build fruitful partnerships with other stakeholders and bring the Regional Authority a step closer to the targeted audience. The RoC created alliances with local, national and international stakeholders, so as to further promote STEP. Since May 2017 the RoC contacted the stakeholders below:

- Technical University of Crete. The public relationships office of the Technical University has supported the promotion of the STEP project during a number of events. Their support not only included the provision of technical facilities (room, internet, etc), but also the dissemination of the STEP project, through their students' mailing lists.
- The P_public group in Chania. It is a very active group with young audience and participants that performs events of various themes, social and environmental. Their events on 10 and 11/06/2017 were focused on the use and accessibility of public space. P_public group promoted the events organized in the framework of STEP to its members.
- The Regional Directorate of Secondary and Primary Education in Heraklion. This stakeholder belongs to the Ministry of Education and not at the Regional Unit.
- The Lawyer's Society of Crete, who participate in a Life project about Environmental Crime. They have also developed an internet platform and application about environmental issues. In collaboration with this stakeholder the RoC had the chance to present STEP in an event at Rethymno (9/6/2017) and during the Themis Conference about environmental Crime.
- The Public Relationship Department of the University of Crete and the Technological Institute of Crete, where also events were organized.

5.2 Mollet del Vallès Municipality (MdV)

STEP became a quite important tool for Mollet del Valles Municipality. Mollet del Valles is a city that has already embraced the concept of civic participation and developed an engaged audience. The STEP platform was a needed component for the existing strategy, designed to strengthen specifically the youth participation in public consultation as it offered an interface designed based on their needs and preferences. In terms of dissemination, Mollet del Valles Municipality has developed an integrated online and offline communication plan, which consists of the organization of various events, two launch events, the production of additional promotional material reported, advertisements at local newspapers, info kiosks, etc.

5.2.1 Dissemination Events

The dissemination activities of Mollet del Valles pilot are briefly presented below.

Table 10MdV Dissemination Activities

Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
Carmanyola Sound	Young people attend this festival that celebrated its 4th edition in the city. It is a one full day festival for Dj's that play music in a public park in Mollet. Young people usually visit the park and spend the whole day with friends. The aim of	-	30/10/2017

	the event was to invite young people to consult on Municipality's Food Policy and make comments and even to volunteer to be part of a group of citizens that will improve the documents and send it to the City council to pass it in a political plenary session. However, the promotion of the STEP project and most of the events were cancelled due to political instability; these days the government of Catalonia declared the Catalan Republic and the independence from the Spanish State.		
Artisans Fair	The aim of the event was to raise awareness about the importance of local and organic products and to promote healthy eating habits and sustainable food systems. This fair gathers thousands of visitors from the city and the province and there is a section dedicated to food. During this period MdV had uploaded a relevant dialogue about healthy and organic food. The expected impact from this event was on the one hand to get the visitors' feedback about the fair organization, and on the other to ask them several questions regarding the local and organic products produced in the rural area of Mollet del Vallès. A stand to promote STEP and the open dialogue was placed. It is estimated that Around 40 young people participated in the dialogue after visiting the stand.	~5,000	15-17/10/2017
Summer City Festival of Mollet del Vallès	This is city's main festival with thousands of attendants and the MdV Municipality allocated a lot of human resources for the promotion of STEP within this Festival. Most of attendants of this festival are young people, since concerts and theater plays for young people are being organized. MdV intended to disseminate the STEP platform and to introduce the participatory process to young citizens. However, the same day the festival started, a deadly terrorists attack took place in la Rambla in Barcelona. As a result, that more than 50 % of the activities of the festival were cancelled, while the participation was quite low. However, even though the results were not the expected ones, it is estimated that STEP was disseminated across the city.	~200	17-22/12/2017

5.2.2 *Communication with local stakeholders*

The citizens of Mollet del Valles were already aware of the participatory concept and familiar with digital tools since the city has been providing the majority of the public services online and employing the participatory budget process for the last few years. However, in order to promote the platform and the dialogues, MdV Municipality established synergies with local stakeholders, who are presented below:

- The MdV Municipality was in close collaboration with the local producers of Gallecs. During the dialogue of the “Artisans Fair”, the producers supported the Municipality with the preparation and the promotion of the dialogue. Additionally, the producers supported the STEP team to create the questionnaire of the dialogue “Gallescsc, el teu park”.
- Additionally, the Municipality is currently collaborating with a secondary school but time is needed in order to come up with results. On December, a workshop was organized within the school in order to demonstrate the Social Media Monitoring Tool to the young students.
- MdV Municipality also visited several stakeholders from the sports and cultural sector and invited them to support STEP, but they didn’t accept to be involved in dialogues. As it is indicated by the pilot manager, nine months are not enough for the promotion of the STEP tool. However, 3 associations from the youth area express their interest and collaborated with the Municipality for the creation of the dialogue: “Call for proposals for young people”. More specifically, they contributed in the content and the dissemination of the dialogue.

5.3 Valdemoro Municipality

Valdemoro Municipality has implemented a number of dissemination activities with a special focus on schools and high school students. One of the Municipality’s basic goals was to inspire behavioral change to this target group and to engage them to participate in decision making from a very early stage. Valdemoro managed to create a precedent of youth engagement and thus this STEP pilot testing period set the starting point for the city to create the missing mechanism for involving youth into the local decision making process. It is important to highlight that new communication channels were created between the Municipality and local stakeholders as well as promising partnerships for implementing a broader and more successful campaign to increase youth engagement and participation in the coming future.

5.3.1 Dissemination Events

The dissemination activities of Valdemoro’s pilot are briefly presented below.

Table 11 Valdemoro’s Dissemination Activities

Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
Valdemoro, educating city	STEP was presented within this event as an example of a democratic participation project. STEP project did a development analysis of the STEP platform and shared with attendees the results of the dialogues and received feedback. Policy makers listened to the results of the dialogues and pledged to motivate youth participation and assist towards a more a sustainable city.	>180	30/11/17
STEP event- award ceremony	STEP organized an award ceremony for the draw and announcement of the dialogue-contest winners. The public draw was performed to select the winners of the dialogues-contests "Eco-Transport" and “Environmental in images”. The event assisted in communicating the project and its activities among the public. Furthermore, the event provided a good	>25	13/11/17

D7.8: 3rd Report on Dissemination Activities

	opportunity to showcase the commitment of STEP project towards the youths and provide credibility to the Municipality.		
Awards for academic excellence	STEP awarded a “Diploma of recognition” to the best academic records of Valdemoro. The aim was bifold a) to motivate the use of the STEP platform and participate in the contests of the platform "Ecological Transport" and "Environment in Images".	165	10/11/2017
Bike day	STEP participated in the “BIKE day” event in the municipality of Valdemoro. A STEP information point was established, to inform participants (students and teachers) of the project and running dialogues. This dissemination activity performed in the frame of and to promote the "Ecological Transport" dialogue.	196 youths 16 teachers	27/10/2017
Workshop with students of secondary education and profesional education	STEP organised the workshop to showcase STEP platform, the dialogues and running contests to young students. The demonstration of the platform was performed in parallel to two running dialogues and attracted significant interest from the participating youths.	>93	27/10/2017
World environment day	STEP participated in the “World Environment day” event in the Cerro del Castillo (Castle Hill) in Valdemoro. A STEP information point was formatted, informing and motivating youths to register and participate in the STEP platform. The dissemination took place in parallel and in support to the “locate and create new green spaces and park areas” dialogue. The citizens of Valdemoro participated in the planting and Irrigation of a hundred trees. The STEP team also distributed small plants to transplant in the hill and in their home.	>120	04/06/17

Figure 52: Workshop with students of secondary education and professional education

Figure 53: BIKE DAY event

Figure 54: STEP event- award ceremony

Figure 55: World Environment Day event

Figure 56: Valdemoro, Educating City event

5.3.2 *Communication with local stakeholders*

In order to increase participation, the Municipality of Valdemoro decided to intensify the dissemination activities for the promotion of the STEP platform to young users. The Municipality of Valdemoro contacted a number of associations and clubs related to the dialogues that were uploaded on the platform. The project also increased Municipality's collaboration with relevant local associations. STEP has managed to involve and bring together different stakeholders (politicians, technicians, teachers, youth, associations, NGOs, etc) to share their opinions. Additionally, during the last months of the open pilot, the Municipality intensified the collaboration with associations and educating centres. To promote participation in the last dialogues they have been in constant contact with the following stakeholders: The Municipality of Valdemoro had regular meetings with a number of stakeholders in order to discuss the progress of the pilot plan and involve them in the STEP activities and events. A list of those contacts performed is attached below:

High Schools

- I.E.S. Villa De Valdemoro (Excellence Baccalaureate)
- I.E.S. Maestro Matías Bravo (International Baccalaureate)
- I.E.S. Ávalon
- I.E.S. Neil Armstrong
- Escuela Comarcal Arzobispo Morcillo (Professional Studies)

Charter Schools

- C.C. San José
- C.C. Samer Calasanz
- C.C. Lagomar
- C.C. Hélicon

C.C. Valle Del Miro
C.C. Nobelis

Private Schools

C. Marqués De Vallejo
C. Nuestra Señora

Other Education Centers

Escuela Municipal De Música Y Danza (Music And Dance)
Escuela Oficial De Idiomas De Valdemoro (Languages)
Escuela De Adultos (Official Courses For Adults. Secondary Education)
Universidad Nacional De Educación A Distancia

Municipality Centers

Centro Ocupacional (Students Taking Part In A Social Risk Project)
La Morada (Young People With Disabilities Who Take Part In A Program To Get Skills Through Pre-Job Activities)

Ecologic Ngo:

Colectivo Espartal Ecologistas En Acción De Valdemoro

Youth Associations:

Group Of Young Volunteers
Asociación Juvenil In Crescendo
Asociación Juvenil Valdemoro Events
Asociación Juvenil Con Otra Mirada
Asociación Juvenil Cazadores De Sueños
Asociación Juvenil Rumbo 33
Asociación Juvenil Minival
Asociación Juvenil Malaba-Ritmo
Asociación Juvenil Kate Millett
Asociación Juvenil Otra Historia
Asociación Juvenil Mármara
Asociación Juvenil Aldaba Danza
Asociación The Lunes-Sección Juvenil
Asociación Amigos Del Jiu Jitsu Brasileño
Asociación Juvenil “La Gruta De Smaug”

Other Associations

Asociación Aiba (Animal)
Asociación Marcha Nordica
Asociación Diversion Y Ocio
Asociación Las Secuoyas
Asociación Con Otra Mirada
Asociación Caballista
Asociación Ornitológica
Asociación Locos Por La Reflex

Asociación Amigos Del Ferrocarril El Platanito

Sport Clubs

Bicidevalde

Agrupación Cicloturista

Asociación Amigos Del Tai Chi, Aikido, Judo.

Club Amigos Del Atletismo

Club Fútbol Inter De Valdemoro

Club Baloncesto Villa De Valdemoro

Club De Natación Villa De Valdemoro

Club De Tenis Mesa Villa Valdemoro

Club De Tenis Valdemoro

Club De Tiro Con Arco Villa De Valdemoro

Club Elemental Gimnasia Rítmica

Club Pescadores "El Carpín"

Club De Ajedrez "La Torre

Club Hockey Steel Acorns

Atlético Valdemoro

Escuela De Futbol Valdemoro

All consultations and discussions with local stakeholders were of great value, a substantial amount of those stakeholders “supported” a number of the implemented dialogues.

5.4 Hatay Metropolitan Municipality

Hatay’s Metropolitan Municipality pilot managed to reach a high percentage of youth participation while at the same time achieved to prioritize the implementation of projects which were proposed on STEP platform by the young participants. This was a quite big challenge for Hatay, since it had to overcome a lot of barriers; the main were the lack of citizens’ participation culture and the lack of previous experience in digital tools.

5.4.1 Dissemination Events

The dissemination activities of Hatay’s pilot are briefly presented below.

Table 12 Hatay’s Dissemination Activities

Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
Open InfoKiosk (c)	InfoKiosks were placed in crowded areas in the city aiming to present the STEP project and platform to the majority of the citizens. One municipality representative and some volunteers, from the core users group, promoted STEP in face to face “sessions” with citizens. This face to face dissemination assisted to reach many young citizens and was also very effective, since It provided the opportunity to chat with the young citizens and explain every detail and highlight the importance of such a tool.	~1,500	16-20/10/2017

D7.8: 3rd Report on Dissemination Activities

InfoKiosk at University (b)	An InfoKiosk was placed in the Mustafa Kemal University aiming to present the STEP project and platform to the majority of the students. STEP was promoted in face to face “sessions” with students. This face to face dissemination assisted to reach many students and was also very effective, since It provided the opportunity to chat with them, explain every detail and highlight the importance of such a tool.	~24,000	18-22/09/2017 & 25-29/09/2017
Open InfoKiosk (b)	InfoKiosks were placed in crowded areas in the city aiming to present the STEP project and platform to the majority of the citizens. One municipality representative and some volunteers, from the core users group, promoted STEP in face to face “sessions” with citizens. This face to face dissemination assisted to reach many young citizens and was also very effective, since It provided the opportunity to chat with the young citizens and explain every detail and highlight the importance of such a tool.	~1,500	14-18/08/2017
InfoKiosk at University	An InfoKiosk was placed in the Mustafa Kemal University aiming to present the STEP project and platform to the majority of the students. STEP was promoted in face to face “sessions” with students. This face to face dissemination assisted to reach many students and was also very effective, since It provided the opportunity to chat with them, explain every detail and highlight the importance of such a tool.	~24,000	8-11/08/2017 & 22-25/08/2017
Training courses (d),	STEP project and platform were disseminated in municipality Education training center. A class by class visit, presentation and promotion of STEP platform and usability was performed. The audience were young citizens and the feedback received was very positive.	~450	17-25/07/2017
Evvel Temmuz Festival	During the Summer the Hatay Metropolitan Municipality is organizing several Concerts for the public. This time the dissemination took place during the Evvel Temmuz Festival, in the Samandağ region. Within this event the Step project and platform were disseminated in collaboration with STEP core users. STEP project hats were also distributed.	~10,000	14/07/2017
Training courses (c), Hatay	STEP project and platform were disseminated in municipality Education training center. A class by class visit, presentation and promotion of STEP platform and usability was performed. The majority of the audience were young citizens and the feedback received was very positive.	~300	11-13/07/2017
Visit to High School	The STEP team visited and promoted the STEP project and platform to youths. Further to explaining to the students what Step is, flyers, hats and pens were distributed. An interactive presentation of the STEP platforms was performed in the School’s Computer room and the Students could directly sign	~200	29/06/2017

D7.8: 3rd Report on Dissemination Activities

	up to the platform. Feedback received was very positive.		
Open InfoKiosk	InfoKiosks were placed in crowded areas in the city aiming to present the STEP project and platform to the majority of the citizens. One municipality representative and some volunteers, from the core users group, promoted STEP in face to face “sessions” with citizens. This face to face dissemination assisted to reach many young citizens and was also very effective, since It provided the opportunity to chat with the young citizens and explain every detail and highlight the importance of such a tool.	~1,500	25- 28/06/2017
Training courses(b), Hatay	STEP project and platform were disseminated in municipality Education training center. A class by class visit, presentation and promotion of STEP platform and usability was performed. The majority of the audience were young citizens and the feedback received was very positive.	~400	12- 15/06/2017
Mustafa Kemal University's Graduate party	STEP project and platform were disseminated during the Mustafa Kemal University's graduate party. A contest was performed during the party to attract the young citizens and we give 3 lucky participants the entrance fee back.	~500	10/06/2017
Training courses, Hatay	STEP project and platform were disseminated in municipality Education training center. A class by class visit, presentation and promotion of STEP platform and usability was performed. The majority of the audience were young citizens and the feedback received was very positive.	~400	07- 09/06/2017
Zara Concert - Hatay	During the Summer the Hatay Metropolitan Municipality is organizing several Concerts for the public. Within this event and during Zara Concert, Zara is a famous in singer in Turkey, the Step project and platform were disseminated. Flyers, hats and pens were also distributed to the concert attendees, and Zara(the singer) made an announcement during the concert with regards to STEP.	~80,000	29/05/2017
Visit to School (b)	The STEP team visited and promoted the STEP project and platform to youths. Further to explaining to the students what Step is, flyers, hats and pens were distributed. An interactive presentation of the STEP platforms was performed in the School's Computer room and the Students could directly sign up to the platform. Feedback was very positive.	~40	26/05/20017
Visit to School	The STEP team visited and promoted the STEP project and platform to youths. Further to explaining to the students what Step is, flyers, hats and pens were distributed. Feedback was very positive.	~150	25/05/2017
Book Fair - Hatay	The Municipality of HATAY organized a 4-day Book Fair event. An InfoKiosk was placed in the event in collaboration with core group users of the Platform. Given that the fair was organized by the HATAY municipality, the STEP project InfoKiosk was positioned in a privileged spot and the promotion of the	~100,000	15- 18/05/2017

D7.8: 3rd Report on Dissemination Activities

	<p>project and platform was very successful. To enhance dissemination activities a contest took place during the Fair and 3 lucky participants were given books from World Classics series.</p>		
<p>Technology days at Hatay Iskenderun Technical University</p>	<p>The Iskenderun Technical University is organizing every year Technology days in the Campus, aiming to enhance and encourage the innovation among students. Within this event STEP placed an InfoKiosk and informed students and citizens visiting about STEP project and STEP platform. Step Project fitted perfectly within the aim of this event, since it enhances innovation through e-participation of Youths. The participants were mostly Students interested to innovation and futuristic projects and the project attracted significant interest.</p>	<p>~7000 Students & ~1000 Citizens</p>	<p>04-06/05/2017</p>

Figure 57: Technology days at Hatay Iskenderun Technical University – STEP InfoKiosk

Figure 58: Book Fair - Hatay– STEP InfoKiosk

Figure 59: Visit to School – STEP

Figure 60: Visit to School (b) - STEP

Figure 61: Zara Concert – Hatay – STEP

Figure 62: Education training center – STEP

Figure 63: Mustafa Kemal University's Graduate party – STEP

Figure 64: Education training center(b) – STEP

Figure 65: Open InfoKiosk – STEP

Figure 66: Visit to High School – STEP

Figure 67: Training courses (c) – STEP

Figure 68: Evvel Temmuz Festival – STEP

Figure 69: InfoKiosk at Mustafa Kemal University – STEP

Figure 70: Training courses (d) - STEP

Figure 71: InfoKiosk at University (b) – STEP

5.4.2 *Communication with local stakeholders*

The pilot team used the broad network of the Municipality to approach the public departments of Hatay area including their representatives and public officers who are interested in environmental issues or youth policies. Therefore, meetings have been conducted with:

- The President and General Secretary of Environmental Protection
- Staff from Promotion and Protection of Environment and Cultural Heritage Foundation
- Staff from Environmental Club of Mustafa Kemal University

Additionally, monthly round table meetings with relevant stakeholders and the core group took place. According to the Municipality the most successful activity for the engagement of the young citizens were the open stands that were established in crowded areas, where a core group of young volunteers were promoting STEP and inviting youngsters to participate in the open dialogues.

5.5 Association of the Communities of Locride area

The Association of Communities of Locride area had developed and performed a very intensive and concrete dissemination plan in order to reach the initially set goals. STEP is considered valuable tool for maintaining relationships between administrators and young people. Apart from Sant'Agata, additional Municipalities expressed their interest in using the STEP platform in order to come closer to young people and involve them in decision making.

5.5.1 Dissemination Events

The dissemination activities of the Association of Communities of Locride area's pilot are briefly presented below.

Table 13 Locride's Dissemination Activities

Title of Activity	Brief description	Reach	Date
STEP Seminar	<p>The aim of the STEP seminar initiative was to present the STEP mobile application for both Android and iOS devices, that will serve to make youth voices heard on environmental issues. Motivated by the effects of pollution on the aesthetics of place and by direct participation in e-democracy the new form of digital democracy animates the whole project.</p> <p>It was also an ideal opportunity to promote the step platform as a tool to make ideas and opinions heard. Furthermore, opportunities were exploited to develop new synergies with organizations and projects, collaboration agreements with third parties, and to strengthen links with public bodies.</p>	~70	11/05/2017
STEP InfoStand	<p>A STEP InfoStand was placed in the Roccella Ionica, Calabria event, in the framework of an event aiming to raise awareness of disease prevention, healthy lifestyle, proper nutrition and to safeguard the environment.</p> <p>The STEP team participated in the event, in order to inform visitors from all over Calabria about the STEP platform and the open dialogues. The audience was mixed, doctors young academic students, environmental fans, sports people and young families with children, young people from Calabria,</p>	~5,000	30/07/2017

	associations and Municipal administrators..		
Sant'Agata del Bianco festival	<p>The Sant'agata del Bianco festival was a prime opportunity for STEP to be disseminated:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - during the music concert, where many tourists and young people of 16 years old to any age were present. During the concert the singer spoke about the Step app and invited the people to download it; - during the book presentation where some volunteers showed how they can use the platform and participate in the dialogues. <i>A presentation of the festival related dialogues was performed "the village of art and flavours"</i>, and people were invited to download the Step app and use the platform through their pc's. <p>Active participation of the STEP project and dissemination of the platform and App during the event, assisted to: increase awareness about the project's outcomes, encourage involvement, as well as to initiate discussions about possible synergies with organisations, collaboration agreements with third existing parties.</p>	~400	01-06/08/2017
Step Platform and App. Presentation	<p>The aim of the Step Platform and App. presentation to: Members of environmental and cultural associations as well as environmental fans, was to involve more young people, including tourists, and the members of the "Mediterranean environment" association in the STEP project. In more detail, to create new relationships, spread awareness of the project and the importance of the e-participation through the step platform.</p> <p>Furthermore, an attempt was performed to understand if the issues are interesting for young adults.</p>	~40	01/09/2017
Treasure hunt/team building game and role playing	<p>The event was organized with general aim to involve young people in step platform, to create awareness about the project's outcomes and to initiate possible collaborations with third parties. The central aim was to involve more young people in the step platform and dialogues, to discuss about step app and to increase STEP project awareness among youths.</p> <p>2 strong benefits derived from this event:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) the participants of the treasure hunt had to use the platform to find a hint, so they had the possibility to familiarize with the dialogues and to read the ideas on Step platform; b) after the "treasure hunt" discussion with the participants was performed, to receive suggestions on the environmental 	~360	10/10/2017

	themes that they prefer to see in the STEP platform.		
Team building activity in the schools entitled: "From Locride to Berlin"	October was a quite intensive month in Locri, since the STEP team visited 4 schools to promote the STEP platform and the open public dialogues. The schools were located at the area of Locri. This dissemination activity was aiming to encourage the participation of young people in using STEP as a tool for dialogue with their peers; The central aim was for students to use the Step platform as a social network to share ideas and information with other peers, even if in different and distant areas.	~800	02-31/10/2017

5.5.2 *Communication with local stakeholders*

In order to engage young citizens in the STEP dialogues, the Association of Municipalities of Locride Area contacted a number of local stakeholders, among which was the President of the Association "Osservatorio ambientale: Diritto per la vita", who explained to the young participants, the importance of respect for nature and raised their awareness on the damage caused by the wrong use of many domestic products. He also highlighted the need to support adequate waste sorting. Among the various activities carried out to promote the Step Project in the Locride area, the Treasure Hunt that took place the 10th September considered to be the most successful event. It was organized by Locride's team of volunteers, involved 60 participants and had a significant impact on the number of users participating in the Pilot.

Additional meetings were held with the main social organizations of the area, NGO's, such as as Civitas Solis, Federazione Mediterraneo, while the cooperation with local schools was enhanced.

5.6 *Resilient Thessaloniki*

The first dialogue of Thessaloniki pilot uploaded on the STEP platform at the end of May. Resilient Thessaloniki uploaded 2 dialogues in total. Resilient Thessaloniki presented the STEP platform in two neighborhood workshops, which were organized in the framework of the first dialogue in June 2017. The main goal of this dialogue was to open up this discussion to a broader audience by asking the citizens to vote the suggested concepts ideas of their preference. The outcome of this dialogue was the selected idea-concept that was implemented at the neighborhood park. Resilient Thessaloniki announced the results to the participants through Social Media Posts, Press releases and interview at the local radio.

Additionally, a Facebook boost campaign was implemented during November in order to promote the 2nd open dialogue to young citizens and to invite them to participate.

6 Dissemination impact indicators

In order to qualify and evaluate the dissemination actions, STEP had set specific measurable goals. The implementation of the dissemination strategy was regularly evaluated according to the level of realisation of dissemination objectives and results set. The following table presents the dissemination impact indicators; the initial target and what has been achieved since the beginning of the project. The STEP team managed to exceed almost all the initially set targets, except from the number of followers in social media accounts and the number of women followers in social media accounts. These targets were quite high from the very beginning and even though the STEP team attempted to reach them, at the end the results were not the ones that were initially set. It should be noted though that the rest of the indicators were successfully achieved and the targets that are presented in the table below have been achieved.

Table 14 Dissemination Impact Indicators

Indicator	Target Value	Achieved since the beginning of the project	Source/ methodology
Number of visits to the project website	45,000	51,128 in the STEP Platform and STEP website	Google analytics
Number of followers in the social media accounts that will be opened	12,000	4,993	Accounts' data
Number of women followers in the social media accounts that will be opened	6,000	2,981	Accounts' data
Number of open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	6	48	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of participants in the open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	1,200	349,325	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of young participants in the open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	800	221,337	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of female participants in the open events (clean-up/ restore events, thematic parades, food festival etc.)	600	122,809	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of targeted events (workshops, roadshows)	12	39	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project

Number of young participants in the targeted events (workshops, roadshows)	500	4,232	Participants' lists
Number of female participants in the targeted events (workshops, roadshows)	300	2,384	Participants' lists
Number of non-project events where STEP project will be presented	6	54	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of entries (articles/ press releases) in local, regional and national press (printed and online)	30	106	Copies of the entries
Number of e-newsletters promoted	10	14	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of newsletters recipients	6,000	<10,000	Mailing list record
Number of distributed printed material	4,000	53,326	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project
Number of viewers of project related audiovisual material	2,000	1,315	Number of views through YouTube
Number of stakeholders registered in the STEP network of interest	1,000	2,710	List of stakeholders
Number of scientific papers published	2	2	Partners' regular reporting on dissemination activities within the project

7 Conclusions

This Dissemination Report provides a complete overview of the dissemination activities concluded in the scope of the STEP project from Month 24 until Month 30 in accordance with the provisions of the 2nd Dissemination Plan.

The main objective of the dissemination activities was to widely disseminate the vision, concept, objectives and innovation of the project, as well as to communicate the results to commercial and general public communities. From the evaluation of these activities, it can be deduced that the performance of the STEP dissemination procedures is quite satisfactory and in accordance with the initial strategy.